

ABSTRACT

Introduction: In Kynotherapy, people receive assistance in rehabilitating and enhancing their personalities from trained dogs. William Tuke founded it because he thought animals might reassure people and instill a sense of responsibility. Kynotherapy has gained popularity due to its ability to elevate mood, lessen discomfort, increase motivation, and enhance interpersonal relationships.

Aims: The purpose of this study is to find out how physiotherapy students feel about Kynotherapy. They want to know whether students think it's beneficial for kids and if it works effectively in rehab.

Materials and Methods: Researchers inquired about the thoughts of Hyderabad physiotherapy students regarding kynotherapy. They spoke with 267 male and female final-year students. They took care to ensure that only seniors were included, leaving out first-year students and those struggling with mental health concerns. They gathered data via a survey and utilized SPSS, a computer programmer, to analyse it.

Result: The majority of students thought kynotherapy was a good idea. They believed it could enhance mood and physical capabilities, aid with social skills, and increase the effectiveness of rehab. They added that it might lessen the boredom and fatigue of lengthy rehab sessions. However, a few students expressed concern that the presence of dogs in treatment could cause distractions or take the place of conventional ways of rehabilitation.

Conclusion: Number of students have agreed that having dogs in therapy can be beneficial. According to them kynotherapy can improve efficiency and social wellbeing. Some students, nevertheless, have certain concerns regarding the education and training of kynotherapists. To them, kynotherapists may not be well-educated and well-trained that could affect their performance. Hence, there should be a certain qualification for kynotherapists.

In general, study indicates the positive views of students concerning the benefits of kynotherapy. Whereas there's need to find solutions of the raised concerns regarding the qualifications of

Kynotherapists. This research gives us a good starting point to explore the potential of Kynotherapy in physiotherapy

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Kynotherapy is a treatment aimed at enhancing rehabilitation outcomes and character enhancement, with the aim of determining physiotherapists' attitudes towards kynotherapy. ^[1] Animal rehabilitation aids patients in developing self-control and calming them, with William Tuke's invention focusing on regular care to instill responsibility for living things. ^[2] Dog therapy involves spontaneous activities with trained dogs, initially conducted by dog lovers and breeders in Poland through organizations. ^[3] Animal-assisted therapy, a treatment method involving trained health practitioners, has shown significant benefits in various populations, including reduced pain, improved mood, increased motivation, and increased patient satisfaction. ^[4] Animals significantly impact human lives, aiding in tasks like food search and house protection, and aiding military and law enforcement in prison guarding and landmine detection, with increased acceptance in Poland over the past 30 years. ^[5] Physical fitness assessments tailored for people with disabilities are essential due to the cognitive processes required for complex motion tasks. ^[6] Kynotherapy is a type of therapy intended to boost the benefits of rehabilitation and support personality development ^[7] William Tuke's rehabilitation method utilized animals for self-control and relaxation, with regular animal care aimed at helping sufferers develop compassion for other living beings, overcoming physical limitations. ^[8] Since ancient times, people have cherished and used animals to enhance their physical and emotional well-being. Using trained animals, animal-assisted therapy is an alternative to conventional medicine ^[9] The use of animal assisted therapy in rehabilitation have benefited a variety of populations, including individuals with reduced pain, improved mood and fatigue, increased motivation and social engagement, and higher patient satisfaction ^[10] Despite the fact that dog-assisted therapy has been around for a while, there are currently few studies that support the effectiveness of the approach. The purpose of the current study was to evaluate the impact of Dog-assisted therapy on children with modest intellectual impairments' psychomotor development ^[11] For nearly 50 years, specially trained ^[12] dogs have been utilized in clinical and home settings to assist children with autism in social interaction and daily activities ^[12] Anxiety disorders are prevalent in children, impacting social, intellectual, and physical functioning. Traditional psychotherapy focuses on cognitive behavioral therapy and parental anxiety management, but recent studies show Animal-assisted therapy's advantages ^[13] The study

- **1.2 Rational of Study:**
 - The aim of the study to find out the beliefs and attitude of students to facilitate and to stimulate physical, intellectual, emotional and social development through multidimensional influence of animals on all human senses.

- **1.3 Objective of Study:**
 - To determine the Physiotherapy student's perception towards kynotherapy.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2016, Mariusz Korczynski et al conducted an experimental study on eight children with Down syndrome to assess the effectiveness of kynotherapy. They used a social functioning assessment sheet before and after kynotherapy to gauge the children's ability to perform activities independently. The results demonstrated significant improvements, with 75% of children showing motivation for therapy (up from 25% initially) and a 75% improvement in the skill of donning and undoing shoes (from an initial 50%). This study concluded that 10 months of kynotherapy enhances independent skills in children with Down syndrome.^[1] **In 2015, Dabrowska et al.** conducted a study on physical therapy students' perceptions of kynotherapy using anonymous questionnaires distributed to sixty third-year students. Results showed that 97% believed certified dogs improved patients' conditions and made therapy more interesting than standard methods, while 66% thought kynotherapy couldn't replace traditional treatment. In conclusion, the study found positive student perceptions of kynotherapy, suggesting its potential as a valuable therapy.^[2]

In 2019, Karen Vizaniaris conducted a qualitative study on therapists' perceptions of animal-assisted therapy, barriers, and motivation. The study involved interviews with speech, physical, and occupational therapists. Results showed a generally positive response to Animal-assisted therapy in professional practice, with 5 of 10 subjects somewhat agreeing and 3 disagreeing on its implementation. Knowledge and belief in Animal-assisted therapy's ability to enhance patient participation and reduce psychological instability were noted. Barriers included organization policies, physical environments, and scheduling issues, but 9 out of 10 participants were still open to implementing Animal-assisted therapy with solutions. However, institutional policies and knowledge gaps hinder Animal-assisted therapy practice^[4]

In 2018, Magdalena Rogoza et al. conducted a study on dog welfare and human-dog interaction in Animal-assisted intervention. They distributed a questionnaire to 64 participants, covering dog and owner characteristics, dog labor, and human-dog interaction. Results showed that 64% of participants reported dogs working 1-2 hours per week, with 50% unsure of therapeutic dog care. About 41% agreed on relaxation procedures like massaging and playing with toys. The study concluded the need for training for kynotherapists to ensure qualifications and the necessity for regulations in animal-assisted interventions to improve practice and rehabilitation programs.^[5]

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS

3.1 Study design:

Cross-sectional study was conducted.

3.2 Setting of study:

The cross-sectional study had been conducted from all institutes of Hyderabad.

3.3 Sampling Method and Sample Size

The sample size had been calculated by a Raosoft sample size calculator, 267 estimated as sample size.

3.4 Sampling Technique

Non probability convenient sampling technique was used.

3.5 Inclusion criteria:

- DPT students were selected.
- Both male and female were selected.
- 4th year and final year students were selected.

3.6 Exclusion criteria:

- Students of 1st year to 3rd year were excluded.
- Participants who were not voluntarily participating were excluded.
- Those participants who had mental and psychological issues were excluded.

3.7 Assessment Tools

The tool was extracted from [Shinozaki M, Fukaya T, Asakawa Y, Ohashi Y. A questionnaire survey of difficulties in clinical practice perceived by physical therapy students. Journal of Physical Therapy Science 2020;32 (12):856-63]

3.8 Data collection procedure

The study design was based on cross-sectional research, in which young healthy university students of 4th and final year were included. Ethical clearance was obtained from

institutional ethical committee. Selection of population were considering inclusion and exclusion criteria. Written consent obtained from the participants.

3.9 Data Analysis Process

Data analysis had done on SPSS VERSION 23

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

4.1 Results

- Regarding the age of respondent in my study is 72.2% from 21 to 23, and 27.3% from 24 to 27 (Table4.1:Figure4.1).
- Regarding the gender of respondent 17.2% were male and 82.8% were female in my study (Table4.2:Figure4.2).
- Regarding the question institution of respondent 36.7% from HIPM&R, 18.0% from HIMAS, 22.8% from AL-BIRUNI, 10.5% from JEEJAL-MAU, 12.0% from ISRA University (Table4.3:Figure4.3).
- Regarding the year of respondent 52.4% from 4th year and 47.6% from 5th (Table4.4:Figure4.4).
- Regarding the question as Kynotherapy may improve an efficiency of physiotherapy it shows about 98.9% agree students and 1.1% students showed their response as disagree (Table4.5:Figure4.5).
- Regarding as Question 2 Kynotherapy is a good way to compliment other method of rehabilitation according to this question students showed their response as agree 96.6% and 3.4% response of students shows disagree (Table4.6:Figure4.6).
- According to Question 3 Kynotherapy may improve social functioning of a patient students display their finding as agree 98.1% and 1.9% result showed as disagree (Table4.7:Figure4.7).
- Question 4 shows Exercises with a trained dog improve patients' frame of mind student response with their displays agree 95.9% and disagree response shows as 4.1% (Table4.8:Figure4.8).
- Based on Question 5 inquiry Kynotherapy may improve patients' dexterity from difficulty of these exercises' students showed their response as agree 97.4% and disagree 2.6% (Table4.9:Figure4.9).
- Given this query as Question 6 Exercises with a trained dog will distract patient's attention show off their reaction as agree 93.6% and disagree rate shows 6.4% (Table4.10:Figure4.10).

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

The cross-sectional study was conducted to comprehend the perspective of a group of students studying physical therapy regarding rehabilitation, where the use of trained and specifically chosen dogs serve as the primary tool and source of motivation for therapy. Physiotherapist's perspectives on the wisdom of using kynotherapy with varying age group was evaluated. The purpose of this research was to find out the knowledge of kynotherapy. The study's findings indicate that it might be difficult to pinpoint physiotherapy student's opinions regarding kynotherapy.

According to my study, the survey found that kynotherapy may replace standard rehabilitation (85.5%). Students are favoring this, and 14.2% believe that Kynotherapy cannot be standard rehabilitation. Regarding students' beliefs in my study (6.7%), students agree that kynotherapy cannot be applied to every age group; it's only for children (93.3%) believe that kynotherapy can be used with every age group, not just children. Most physiotherapy students, though the majority of these activities are enjoyed by children, the survey found that kynotherapists who are not physiotherapists typically conduct rehabilitation in the wrong way (77.9% of students agreed, while 12.4% disagreed). According to my study, the question was whether kynotherapy could strengthen the effectiveness of physiotherapy as a complement to other methods of improvement. 96.6 percent of students agreed with that statement, and 3.4% of students showed a negative response to this question. The majority of students think that engaging in activities with a trained dog causes patients to concentrate on the dog rather than the task at hand. Regarding the question, 94.8 percent of students agreed that exercises with a trained dog improve the therapist's interaction with a patient, and 5.2% of students disagreed with this statement. The majority of physiotherapy students have discovered that having a therapy dog increases participant's willingness to exercise. In our study, the survey found that exercise with a trained dog will distract patient's attention. The majority of students agreed with that statement, and according to them, when we add the dog to our treatment program, the patient's focus is taken off the work. Exercise with a trained dog will focus patients' dislike of ordinary rehabilitation (84.3%) students agree with this survey their thoughts where patients will not

enjoy standard rehabilitation when they exercise with a trained dog and (15.7%) students showed their response against this statement their thoughts were different that's why they did not agree to this survey. Working with trained dogs may weaken fatigue and boredom connected to long-term rehabilitation. In this survey, the majority of students thought mental stimulation makes your animal more tired than physical stimulation.

In a previous study conducted by **Fizjoterapia in 2015**, he found that kynotherapy may replace standard rehabilitation, as confirmed by 66% of students. According to his study, students claimed that kynotherapy was more engaging and uplifted mood than therapy that doesn't involve pets. Regarding his study, 65% of physiotherapy students believe that kynotherapy can be used with any age group, not just children (62%). According to his research, all age groups respond well to kynotherapy. Dogs help people's mental, cognitive, and motor development. As an addition to other methods of improvement, physiotherapy students claim that kynotherapy can enhance the efficacy of physiotherapy. According to his survey, it's unclear if working with a trained dog enhances communication between a patient and therapist. Physiotherapy students who were questioned about it in the survey attested to the claim. Students think that because a patient has a dog, they are more likely to exercise, which improves mobility and makes the therapy more engaging, a belief that other researchers have also confirmed. According to his survey, the students claimed that kynotherapy might increase physiotherapy's efficacy. 31 respondents attested to the fact that kynotherapy enhances other forms of treatment and may help patients' social functioning. Nearly all respondents said that it was more engaging than receiving standard therapy without a dog (97%). Half of the students disagreed with the claim that kynotherapists lack the necessary training, making the improvements they make ineffective, and 44% had no opinion. According to his study, a majority of students think that engaging in activities with a trained dog causes patients to focus on the dog rather than the task at hand, and that the patient's attention is diverted from the task. The efficacy of rehabilitation is decreased when a therapist spends half of his time with the patient and the dog during kynotherapy. 65% of respondents disagreed with this as assertion. Additionally, according to more than half of those surveyed, it is unfair to argue that kynotherapy is exclusively effective with youngsters. In his study regarding Pearson's correlation coefficient calculations, there was no relationship between the respondent's independent variables (respondents' age and sex, previous education, year of participation in the physical therapy college, current status as licensed physiotherapists, and whether or not they had heard of kynotherapy before) and the students' attitude towards kynotherapy.

Regarding his study, when people with a variety of diseases interact with dogs, their motor, mental, and intellectual development is improved.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

- **6.1 Conclusion**

- Number of students have agreed that having dogs in therapy can be beneficial. According to them Kynotherapy can improve efficiency and social wellbeing. Some students, nevertheless, have certain concerns regarding the education and training of Kynotherapists. To them, Kynotherapists may not be well-educated and well-trained that could affect their performance. Hence, there should be a certain qualification for Kynotherapists. In general, study indicates the positive views of students concerning the benefits of kynotherapy. Whereas there's need to find solutions of the raised concerns regarding the qualifications of Kynotherapists .This research gives us a good starting point to explore the potential of Kynotherapy in physiotherapy.

- **6.2 Strengths**

- Several neurological disorders, including cerebral palsy, Down syndrome, mental retardation, and stroke, may be treated by using Kynotherapy.
- Kynotherapy also makes the at-home rehabilitation program easier; it might not need a rehabilitation facility, etc.
- Patients who enjoy animals or are interested in canines may fully participate.
- Dogs help patients perform their ADLs better as well.

- **6.3 Weaknesses**

- Kynotherapy required well-trained animals like dogs, etc.
- It is difficult to manage those people who have allergies to dogs, known as kynophobia.
- Required highly skilled and trained therapists. Additionally, ensuring the safety and well-being of both the animals and the individuals involved requires careful management and training.

- **6.4 Recommendations**

- Kynotherapy can be used in various healthcare departments including hospitals, rehabilitation centers, and private clinics.

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